

Dexarch - Revolutionising Archaeozoological Data Documentation and Collaboration with Mobile Technology

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Abstract

Archaeozoology, the study of animal remains from archaeological contexts, plays a central role in reconstructing past human–animal interactions, subsistence strategies, and environmental conditions. Documenting faunal remains is critical in archaeozoology, requiring detailed recording of attributes such as provenance, taxon, and anatomy, taphonomy (study of post-mortem processes affecting remains), and measurements, among others. Despite the increasing use of digital tools across archaeology, archaeozoology continues to rely heavily on paper-based documentation methods that are labour-intensive, error-prone, and challenging for collaboration.

This paper aims to highlight the main benefits of the Dexarch application in archaeozoological research. Dexarch is a mobile application designed specifically for archaeozoological data documentation and collaboration. The app was developed to address the limitations of existing digital tools, which are either general-purpose or too complex for practical field use. Built with Flutter and integrated with Firebase Firestore, the app supports secure user authentication, offline data entry, and robust data synchronisation upon reconnection.

Keywords: Archaeozoology, Taphonomy, Digital Documentation, Mobile Application, Flutter, Firebase,

24 **1. Introduction**

25 Archaeology as a discipline has undergone a major transformation via digital technologies in the past few
26 decades. For instance, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), 3D scanning, and digital repositories have
27 all reshaped how archaeologists collect, analyse, and disseminate both small and big data (Spyrou et al.
28 2022). However, not all sub-disciplines have experienced this digital transition and evolution equitably.
29 Archaeozoology, a sub-discipline of archaeology, involves studies of past animal remains such as bones,
30 teeth, and shells found from archaeological explorations or excavations. Despite its crucial role in
31 reconstructing past economies, environments, and cultural practices, the subject still lags behind in
32 adopting digital-first workflows.

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34 Documenting faunal remains is critical in archaeozoology, requiring detailed recording of attributes such
35 as their provenance, taxon, and anatomy, taphonomy (study of post-mortem processes affecting remains),
36 and measurements, among others. Traditionally, researchers have relied on paper-based methods,
37 manually recording findings in field notebooks, laboratory forms, or outdated versions of MS Excel. While
38 these manual techniques have been effective for decades, they have significant drawbacks: they are
39 labour-intensive, prone to human error, and introduce logistical challenges, particularly in data sharing
40 and collaboration. Furthermore, reliance on paper exacerbates problems of data loss, archiving, and
41 reproducibility. In an era where mobile technologies are rapidly transforming how information is gathered
42 and shared, archaeozoology lags behind, while other archaeological sub-disciplines have already
43 embraced digital solutions. This digital gap hinders the progress of research, archiving, and collaboration.

44
45 While some solutions have emerged in recent years in the digital space, including DigApp, TaphonomApp,
46 and I.L.I.U.M. (Martín-Perea et al. 2020; Montagnetti and Guarino 2011), these tools can be generic,
47 technically complex, or insufficiently tailored to the specific workflows of archaeozoologists. In many
48 regions, particularly South Asia, field archaeozoologists operate in low-connectivity environments,
49 necessitating offline capabilities and lightweight, intuitive applications. In this context, we introduce
50 Dexarch, a dedicated mobile application for archaeozoological documentation. This innovation aims to
51 bridge this gap by offering a dedicated mobile application that is simple yet powerful, meeting
52 archaeozoologists' unique needs both in and out of the field.

53
54 This paper details the conception, technical development, and deployment of Dexarch. We present its
55 database schema, technical infrastructure, and user interface design. We also discuss how its features -
56 ranging from offline geolocation to collaborative group functions- address both long-standing and
57 emerging challenges in archaeozoological research.

58

59 **2. Methods and Materials**

60 **2.1 Development Rationale and UI Design**

61 The development of Dexarch began by identifying and analysing the primary needs of archaeozoologists
62 to ensure the application aligned with the discipline's unique requirements. Interviews with researchers
63 highlighted several critical requirements - structured data recording, offline usability, ease of use, and
64 collaboration features. The design phase included creating user interface wireframes in Adobe Illustrator,
65 which were refined through multiple iterations to enhance usability and ensure intuitive navigation.

66

67 **2.2 Database Design**

68 The Dexarch database amalgamates field-tested recording schemas developed in two decades of
69 archaeozoological work by the third author across her projects in Italy, France, and India, in conjunction
70 with published internationally standardised protocols (Behrensmeyer 1978; Fernández-Jalvo et al. 2016;
71 Grant 1982; Hillson 2005; Lyman 1994; Payne 1973; Reitz and Wing 1999). The database is structured into
72 three major categories of fields:

- 73 • Context and Coordinates: Records excavation unit, trench, stratum, orientation, dip, and
74 associated remains (Fig 1).
- 75 • Identification: Captures taxonomic and anatomic classification, fragment size, laterality,
76 associated number, and wearing stage (for teeth) (Fig 2).
- 77 • Taphonomy: Documents various human and non-human generated modifications on bones such
78 as calcination, shaft length, circumference, fracture pattern, weathering stage, concretion,
79 encrustation, trampling, later intrusions, pathology, and butchery marks (Fig 3).

80

81 These categories provide comprehensive coverage of faunal attributes, ensuring that Dexarch can
82 substitute paper notebooks without sacrificing detail.

83

84 **2.3 Technical Infrastructure**

85 Built with Flutter, Google's open-source software development kit, Dexarch is designed for cross-platform
86 compatibility; while currently available only for Android, the use of Flutter allows for future expansion to
87 iOS. Firebase Authentication is used to secure user access via email or Google accounts, and Firebase
88 Firestore serves as our cloud database. We chose Firebase because of its seamless integration with Flutter
89 and its robust offline data persistence capabilities, which are provided by Cloud Firestore, a flexible NoSQL
90 database. The combination ensures that entries added by the user are cached locally when offline and
91 synchronised with the cloud once connectivity is restored, guaranteeing little to no data loss.

92

93 Fig 1. Attributes related to the context and coordinates of the bone remains incorporated in the app.

94

95

96 Fig 2. Identification-related attributes incorporated in the app.

97
98 Fig 3. Taphonomy-related attributes incorporated in the app.

99
100 **3. Results**

101 **3.1 Overview**

102 The development and testing of Dexarch yielded a field-ready mobile application that is both robust and
103 user-friendly, designed to streamline archaeozoological data documentation, enhance collaboration, and
104 ensure data security. Dexarch implements a four-stage, structured recording workflow (Context and
105 Coordinates; Identification; Taphonomy; Notes) while integrating multimedia, mapping, and sharing
106 features. The system has three complementary design goals:

- 107 • Enable fast, standardised and accurate data capture at the point of discovery
- 108 • Support collaborative research while preserving user control over data
- 109 • Remain resilient where networks are unreliable.

110 The following subsections present the current features and results, followed by planned future
111 developments that expand its potential (Fig 4).

112
113 **3.2 Authentication, Access Control and Security**

- 114 • **Authentication:** User accounts are created via Firebase Authentication (email/password and
115 Google OAuth). Users can view and manage their data only after their emails are verified.
- 116 • **Access Control:** Database security rules (Firestore rules) enforce per-user write privileges so users
117 may only modify entries they own or entries that have been explicitly shared with them. This
118 guarantees that no entry can be accessed or altered without proper authorisation.
- 119 • **Security:** Data held in Firestore and Firebase Storage benefits from the cloud provider’s encryption
120 at rest.

121

122 3.3 Data Management Workflow

- 123 ● **Add and Manage Entries:** Users can create new entries for faunal remains, recording various
124 attributes like locational coordinates, taphonomic signatures, and skeletal measurements. Data is
125 collected in four stages: context and coordinates, identification, taphonomy, and notes. This
126 structured approach standardises the data collection process across different users. Additionally,
127 users can upload photos of fields and related elements to enrich the data entries visually.
- 128 ● **Edit and Delete Entries:** Dexarch allows entries to be updated at any stage. Users can edit saved
129 entries and resubmit changes to the database. Users can also delete erroneous records.
- 130 ● **Star Entries:** Users may also “star” important entries for rapid access, helping manage large
131 datasets and highlighting high-priority records.
- 132 ● **Custom Filters and Sorting:** Users can filter entries based on attributes like location, taphonomy,
133 or site and sort them by parameters, such as date created or date modified, simplifying
134 management of large datasets.

135

136 3.4 Offline Capabilities

- 137 ● **Offline Data Entry:** Given the frequent lack of reliable internet connectivity in field archaeology,
138 Dexarch allows users to add entries offline, caching textual data locally. Once the device reconnects
139 to the internet, cached data syncs with the cloud, ensuring no information is lost. A local lightweight
140 database stores images until they can be uploaded; a background worker manages uploads to
141 Firebase Storage.
- 142 ● **Offline Location Detection:** Dexarch supports offline location services by allowing users to
143 download maps tiles for an area ahead of time. Users can download the maps of the area (where
144 the faunal remains are) and can use the map to pinpoint the location of the faunal remains and add
145 it to the entry. This feature is particularly useful for archaeozoologists working in remote locations,
146 enabling accurate geolocation of faunal remains even without a live internet connection.

147

148 3.5 Privacy, Sharing Controls and Settings

- 149 ● **Public / Private Profiles:** Users choose whether their profile is discoverable. Public profiles are
150 searchable by name; private profiles are invisible to in-app searchers unless the user permits
151 discovery by email or direct invitation.
- 152 ● **Timed Sharing:** Shared entries can be given an explicit expiry (time-limited access). After the
153 sharing period expires, the shared users lose access to the entry, adding an extra layer of privacy.
- 154 ● **Settings Page:** A dedicated settings module allows users to configure: profile visibility; whether
155 others can add them as friends or add them to groups; push and/or email notifications (on/off and
156 per-event settings); and data export preferences.

157 **3.6 Collaboration and Data Sharing**

- 158 • **Friends and Groups:** Friends are quick-sharing contacts; groups are project units for multi-user
159 collaboration. Users can search for collaborators by name (if public) or email (if the other user
160 permits lookup) and add them as friends. Users can also create groups within the app, facilitating
161 team-based research projects. Group members can share entries with each other, streamlining
162 collaboration on multisite or multi-project research.
- 163 • **Invitations:** Invitations for friends / groups may be sent in-app; users receive push and/or email
164 notifications when invited or added. Notifications are configurable in Settings.
- 165 • **In-App Data Sharing:** Users can share their entries with other users (if sharing is permitted by
166 them) for a specified time period, enhancing collaboration.
- 167 • **Export and Import Entries:** Dexarch supports exporting data in multiple formats, including Excel
168 and JSON, which allows users to easily share their research with others or analyse data outside the
169 application. It also supports importing entries via JSON files, ensuring flexibility in data
170 management.

171

172 **3.7 Personalisation**

173 Users may edit name, affiliation, short bio, avatar (image), gender, and see the login email. Display of email
174 may be toggled for privacy. Users can also control whether they appear in search and whether their email
175 is discoverable.

176

177 **3.8 Feedback and Versioning**

178 Dexarch includes an in-app feedback form, allowing users to report issues or request features. : Users get
179 notified whenever a new version of Dexarch is released to the app store, ensuring that they have the latest
180 features available for use. Updates and version information are also delivered through release notes on
181 the Play Store. This feedback loop ensures that development remains community-driven and responsive
182 to archaeologists' real needs.

183

184 **3.9 Scalability and Architecture**

185 Dexarch's backend relies on Firebase Firestore, a NoSQL database that enables efficient querying and
186 automatic scaling. The structure supports thousands of entries without performance degradation. Data
187 caching and lazy loading minimise network calls, while asynchronous uploads maintain responsiveness.
188 Images are uploaded at configurable resolutions to balance storage and bandwidth. Background
189 synchronisation is rate-limited to preserve battery life and data allowances. The modular architecture
190 allows future integration with institutional databases and external repositories such as Zenodo or Open
191 Context.

192

193 **3.10 Planned and Future Developments**

- 194
- 195 • **iOS:** Release an iOS version of the application, leveraging Flutter’s cross-platform compatibility.
 - 196 • **Quick Edit Function:** Inline editing directly from the home screen for faster corrections.
 - 197 • **Interactive Tutorial/Onboarding:** A guided onboarding walkthrough will introduce first-time users to the four-stage workflow, exporting, sharing and maps.
 - 198 • **In-app Analytics:** Dashboards summarise taxa frequency, taphonomic signatures, spatial distributions (heatmaps), and recent activity to support immediate field decisions about sampling or targeted recording.
 - 199 • **Role-Based Permissions:** Group owners will be able to assign project-specific roles (owner, editor, viewer) to members to improve multi-level collaboration.
 - 200 • **Virtual Bone Library:** A reference repository of annotated skeletal images and 3D models for field identification.
- 201
- 202
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- 205

206 Fig 4. Top Features of Dexarch

207

208 **4. Discussion**

209 In today's quickly evolving digital world, the ongoing use of paper-based documentation in
210 archaeozoology is becoming increasingly unsustainable, especially as digitisation becomes critical for
211 archival preservation. Museums and archaeological groups are facing serious storage limits for physical
212 records, emphasising the urgent need to implement digital data management from the start of the
213 exploration or excavation process. This shift promises significant improvements in both time efficiency
214 and resource conservation.

215
216 Digitisation is not merely a matter of convenience but of long-term preservation. Paper records degrade,
217 whereas digital entries—when stored redundantly in the cloud and institutional archives—offer resilience.
218 Dexarch thus contributes to archival sustainability, bridging excavation and long-term data management.
219 Furthermore, Dexarch aligns with principles of open science. Enabling export in open formats and
220 supporting free access democratises archaeozoological research, particularly in regions with limited
221 resources for commercial software.

222

223 **5. Conclusion**

224 Dexarch represents a paradigm shift for archaeozoological practice by embedding digital documentation
225 directly into fieldwork. By uniting structured data fields, offline capabilities, collaborative functions, and
226 open data export, Dexarch addresses long-standing barriers to efficiency, accuracy, and reproducibility.

227

228 Its free availability, intuitive design, and adaptability to low-connectivity environments make Dexarch
229 especially impactful in the Indian context, where paper-based methods remain dominant. At the same
230 time, its design is sufficiently generalisable for global adoption. As archaeozoology embraces digitisation,
231 Dexarch provides a scalable, sustainable, and open-access solution that enhances research quality while
232 fostering collaboration across institutions and regions.

233

234 **6. Acknowledgements**

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236 Centre. We also thank all users who provided invaluable feedback and testing insights.

237

238 **7. Data Accessibility Statement**

239 Dexarch application is available for free on the Google Play Store (Android 7.0+). The database schema and
240 the APK (Android Application Package) file are uploaded to Zenodo.

241

242

243 **8. Conflict of Interest Disclosure**

244 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation
245 to the content of the article.

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